

D6.1 - First report on the optimization and evolution of EPOS RI

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Deliverable Abstract

Deliverable D6.1 provides the first annual recommendations for the optimization and evolution of the EPOS Research Infrastructure (EPOS RI), based on EPOS ON first-year activities (M1–M12). It consolidates key outcomes from the project's activities and presents them as concrete actions for the EPOS ERIC Service Coordination Committee (SCC), discussed within the Optimization and Evolution Board and with the SCC, in alignment with the EPOS ERIC Science Program 2024–2028.

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QUALITY CONTROL

Date	Name	Organisation
Reviewers:	Optimization and Evolution Board (OEB)	UU; INGV; CNRS; ORB

TERMINOLOGY

Acronym	Definition
AB	Advisory Board
ECR	Early Career Researcher
ENVRI	European network of ENVironmental Research Infrastructures
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ICS	Integrated Core Services
OEB	Optimization and Evolution Board
SCC	Service Coordination Committee
TCS	Thematic Core Service
WP	Work Package

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Executive summary

Deliverable D6.1, developed under WP6 Task 6.1 “*Analysis of project outputs in relation to the EPOS Sustainability Plan*” of the EPOS ON project, presents the first set of recommendations for the optimization and evolution of the EPOS Research Infrastructure (EPOS RI). The deliverable is based on the activities and results achieved during the first year of the project (September 2024 – August 2025, M1–M12).

The deliverable provides: (i) a consolidated overview of the key results relevant to EPOS RI optimization and evolution achieved across Work Packages WP2–WP6; and (ii) a structured set of recommendations, formulated as concrete actions addressed to the EPOS ERIC Service Coordination Committee (SCC). These actions have been identified by the Optimization and Evolution Board (OEB) based on the analysis of project outputs and were shared and discussed with the SCC in the framework of the established OEB-SCC interaction.

1. Introduction

The EPOS ON project aims to support the optimization and evolution of the EPOS Research Infrastructure (EPOS RI) by enhancing services for science (WP2), contributing to tackling societal challenges (WP3), strengthening impact through user engagement (WP4), enlarging European and international collaborations (WP5), and further engaging national stakeholders and developing an integrated management tool (WP6), in alignment with, and supporting the implementation of, the EPOS Science Program 2024–2028.

Deliverable *D6.1 - First report on the optimization and evolution of EPOS RI*, builds on the internal reporting process implemented across WP2–WP6. Work Package leaders submit Internal Reports every six months using a common template agreed at the start of the project with WP1 and the Optimization and Evolution Board (OEB). The first reporting cycle (submitted in March 2025) covered M1–M6 (September 2024 – February 2025), while the second reporting cycle (submitted in early September 2025) covered M7–M12 (March 2025 – August 2025). WP6 consolidated these inputs into a Summary Report, discussed within the OEB, which provided the basis for identifying key results and formulating recommendations.

Recommendations in this deliverable are presented as concrete actions for the EPOS ERIC Service Coordination Committee (SCC). The SCC, representing both Thematic Core Services (TCS) and Integrated Core Services (ICS), is formally engaged in EPOS ON as a beneficiary and plays a central role in supporting the Executive Director in the formulation and implementation of the EPOS Annual Work Plan, by monitoring the operational performance of the infrastructure and ensuring the effective integration of project results into the EPOS Delivery Framework.

The Summary Report prepared by WP6, consolidating the key outcomes of the first project year and the recommendations formulated as actions, was shared with the SCC. It was discussed during the event “*Optimization and Evolution of the EPOS Research Infrastructure*” (1–2 October 2025), which brought together the Optimization and Evolution Board (OEB), the EPOS ERIC Service Coordination Committee (SCC) and Executive Committee (EC), and the EPOS ON Advisory Board (AB) to discuss activities supporting the optimization and evolution of EPOS RI. This deliverable provides an initial overview of first-year results and recommendations, which will be monitored and refined over the project lifetime and consolidated in *D6.2 - Final report on the optimization and evolution of EPOS RI* due in June 2027.

2. Key results relevant to the optimization and evolution of the EPOS Research Infrastructure

This chapter summarises the key results achieved during the first year of the EPOS ON project that are relevant to the optimization and evolution of EPOS RI and that informed the formulation of recommendations presented as actions. Results are presented by Work Package (WP2–WP6) and reflect progress in service development, societal impact, user engagement, international collaboration, and governance and sustainability.

2.1. WP2 – Enhancing Services for Science

During the reporting period, WP2 strengthened the foundations for expanding and consolidating the EPOS service portfolio. A key result was the finalization of Deliverable [D2.1](#)¹, which defines a structured roadmap for the integration of new and enhanced services into EPOS over the period 2025–2027. The roadmap provides a clear implementation timeline aligned with EPOS quarterly development cycles and the ICS–TCS Interaction framework, covering a broad range of multidisciplinary datasets, thematic services, and database evolutions.

WP2 also advanced the integration of new scientific communities and stakeholders. In particular, the approach for integrating the Built Environment Data community was structured around the EPOS Implementing Rules, and largely supported by Deliverable [D2.2](#)², which provides practical guidance for the establishment of new thematic services within EPOS. In parallel, initial engagement with external stakeholders, including initiatives and private actors, explored cooperation opportunities and data exchange models.

In addition, WP2 carried out preparatory work on computational Earth science tools, including a landscape analysis of existing tools and the identification of relevant use cases. Initial developments on software environments, modelling tools, and high-performance computing resources laid the groundwork for future integration of computational services into the EPOS ecosystem.

2.2. WP3 – Contribution to Tackling Societal Challenges

WP3 delivered significant results aimed at strengthening EPOS contributions to societal challenges, particularly in the areas of risk management, ethical governance, and environmental sustainability. Progress was made in the development and enhancement of scientific products and prototypes supporting earthquake early warning, tsunami and meteotsunami forecasting, exposure and risk modelling, and warning communication.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/14972383>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17136145>

Key outcomes include the operational use and further development of early warning components, the expansion of forecasting capabilities to broader geographic scales, and the availability of data and prototype services through open repositories and web-based interfaces. These developments support the integration of EPOS services into operational and decision-support contexts.

In addition, WP3 initiated interaction with operational stakeholders in civil protection and disaster risk management. Collaboration was started with relevant actors by establishing contacts with the European Response Coordination Centre (ERCC) and the Union Civil Protection Knowledge Network (UCPKN) to strengthen science–policy links. A key step was a dedicated meeting (Bruxelles, April 2025) with the UCPKN to clarify EPOS ON needs and to frame expected contributions from the Union Civil Protection Mechanism (UCPM), including outreach to broader communities, engagement with national and local authorities, and support to communication and media activities.

WP3 also initiated cross-cutting frameworks relevant to EPOS service provision. Work began on developing an EPOS ethical framework, including a Community Position Paper on Ethics and a prototype of a standardised ethical label for services. In parallel, WP3 began the mapping of EPOS services against the UN Sustainable Development Goals, providing an initial structured basis for environmental assessment and sustainability-related analysis of EPOS digital services.

2.3. WP4 – Strengthening Impact Through User Engagement

During the reporting period, WP4 advanced in strengthening user engagement, broadening participation, and consolidating the EPOS community. A key outcome was the timely delivery of the Activity Plan for User Interaction ([D4.1](#)³). The plan sets out a comprehensive roadmap to expand and diversify the user base, structured around four pillars: attracting new users, training users to become proficient with the EPOS Platform, collecting feedback to improve services, and rewarding and retaining users through incentives. The strategy is designed as a cyclical process, ensuring incremental improvements and sustainability beyond the project’s end. Complementary activities included preparations for the renewal of the User Feedback Groups and the analysis of roadblocks to platform adoption. In connection to the latter point, work progressed on vocabulary harmonisation, improving consistency and interoperability across services.

WP4 also focused on strengthening participation and dialogue with the community through communication and training activities. A flagship achievement was the organisation of [EPOS Days 2025](#)⁴ ([Perugia, March 2025](#)), which attracted broad international participation. New interactive formats such as meet & greet sessions were successfully introduced, fostering inclusiveness and direct exchange between stakeholders.

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14973199>

⁴ <https://events.epos-eu.org/event/21/>

A particular emphasis was placed on empowering Early Career Researchers (ECRs). Thanks to targeted support measures, ECR participation in EPOS Days more than doubled compared to the previous year. ECRs were actively involved through flash talks and posters, presenting their research and expectations for the EPOS Platform. In parallel, preparations for the first [EPOS Summer School⁵ \(Olot, Spain, June 2025\)](#) were completed, focusing on training in open and FAIR data management in geosciences. These initiatives increased visibility for ECRs, reinforced their role as active contributors, and laid the foundation for long-term engagement with EPOS services.

2.4. WP5 – Enlarging European and International Collaborations

During the reporting period, WP5 strengthened EPOS positioning at European and international levels by consolidating strategic partnerships and establishing new cooperation frameworks with key research infrastructures and initiatives. At the European level, WP5 advanced pan-European collaborations through the implementation and renewal of Memorandum of Understanding with key partners, including EUMETNET, EUREF, ECCSEL, EuroGeoSurveys, and the ENVRI community. These collaborations resulted in joint meetings, coordinated activities, and the identification of concrete synergies in areas such as data and metadata harmonisation, interoperability, service complementarity, and joint outreach. Notable outcomes include the renewal of the EPOS–EuroGeoSurveys MoU, progress towards formalising collaboration with EuroGeographics, continued integration efforts with ECCSEL services, and EPOS leadership in the development of the ENVRI-Hub service catalogue.

At the international level, WP5 established a structured framework for global cooperation, with the delivery of Deliverable [D5.2⁶](#), the *Roadmap for the Implementation of International Collaboration*. During the first project year, substantial progress was achieved with partners such as AuScope, EarthScope, and Earth Sciences New Zealand through joint proposals, shared visibility at international fora, the launch of a Global Infrastructure Collaboration webinar series, and the drafting of a multi-party Memorandum of Understanding. Cooperation was also initiated with partners in Africa and Latin America, with a focus on capacity building, disaster risk reduction, and engagement with local Earth science communities.

WP5 further expanded EPOS engagement with global and thematic initiatives, including GEM, GTM, GEO-GSNL, WOVO/vHub, and emerging communities such as Muography, through joint events, technical exchanges, and exploratory discussions on data sharing and service integration. In parallel, WP5 contributed to EPOS engagement within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem by monitoring developments, participating in EOSC-related working groups, interacting with other

⁵ <https://events.epos-eu.org/event/26/>

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14973412>

ERICs on shared priorities, and contributing to proposal preparation under Horizon Europe 2025 calls.

Overall, WP5 results strengthened EPOS strategic partnerships, improved coordination of European and international collaboration activities, and reinforced EPOS visibility and coherence within both the global research infrastructure landscape and the EOSC ecosystem.

2.5. WP6 – Optimization and Evolution of the EPOS Research Infrastructure

As described in the Introduction, WP6 implemented a common internal reporting framework, developed with WP1 and the Optimization and Evolution Board (OEB), to monitor progress across the project and consolidate first-year results relevant to EPOS RI optimization and evolution. Two reporting cycles were completed, and the resulting summary reports, discussed within the OEB and shared with the SCC, supported the identification of cross-cutting outcomes and the formulation of recommendations presented as actions for EPOS governance bodies.

WP6 also advanced engagement with national stakeholders by carrying out a comprehensive desk mapping of the national landscapes of the countries participating in the EPOS Delivery Framework. The mapping collected structured information on EPOS membership, national representation, funding, participation in EPOS activities, and economic aspects. These data were already used by EPOS ERIC to support discussions within the EPOS ERIC General Assembly on membership contributions. During the reporting period, WP6 also contributed to the organisation of the session “EPOS in the National Landscapes” at EPOS Days 2025, which highlighted national perspectives on embedding EPOS within research strategies, funding frameworks, and multidisciplinary initiatives. Based on the mapping results and the outcomes of the session, preparations were initiated for the establishment of a dedicated task force to enhance coordination and communication between EPOS ERIC and the National Clusters.

In parallel, WP6 strengthened engagement with national authorities through the establishment of the National Authorities Consultation Board (NACB), formally created in February 2025 with the participation of representatives from Finland, Slovak Republic and Türkiye. The NACB brings together representatives from national ministries and research organisations and aims to strengthen links with countries involved in EPOS RI, including those not yet EPOS ERIC Members. The first NACB meeting has been held in September 2025 to discuss EPOS status, participation in integration activities, and next steps for national engagement.

Finally, WP6 delivered key results in support of EPOS ERIC management and sustainability through the definition of the technical requirements for an integrated Back-Office tool. A comprehensive technical specification was produced and submitted as Milestone 25, providing the reference for the development phase. The work focused on long-term sustainability, regulatory compliance, and interoperability with the EPOS Platform, and generated interest from other ERICs, confirming the

broader relevance of the approach. The launch of the call for tender in July 2025 marked the transition from planning to implementation.

3. Recommendations for the Optimization and Evolution of EPOS RI

This chapter consolidates the recommendations emerging from the first year of EPOS ON activities (M1–M12). The recommendations are derived from the key results achieved across WP2–WP6 and from discussions held within the Optimization and Evolution Board (OEB) and with the EPOS ERIC Service Coordination Committee (SCC). They are addressed to the SCC and formulated as concrete actions, consistent with its role within the EPOS Delivery Framework in supporting the Executive Director in the EPOS Annual Work Plan and monitoring the infrastructure’s operational performance.

The recommendations are presented in Table 1 as *Actions for the SCC*. For each action, the table reports the Work Package(s) from which the action originates and the alignment with the Strategic Objectives (SO) of the EPOS Science Program 2024–2028.

Table 1: Actions for the Service Coordination Committee (SCC)

Action ID	Action description	Alignment with EPOS Science Program 2024–2028
WP2	A1. The SCC, in coordination with EPOS ERIC, should ensure that the D2.1 roadmap remains closely aligned with the ICS–TCS Interaction Cycle, to maintain coherence with EPOS’s established integration methodologies.	SO1, SO2, SO4, SO5
	A2. The SCC should oversee the progress of the Built Environment Data community in its efforts to become a Candidate TCS. Additionally, because of some pioneering questions, discussions should be planned on potential formal collaboration frameworks for private sector engagement (e.g., legal agreements, data provision mechanisms).	
WP3	A1. The SCC should further support the TCS Ethics representatives by fostering regular communication on the topic in the TCS consortium meetings.	SO1, SO2, SO3, SO4, SO5, SO6.
	A2. The SCC should support the identification of missing TCS contact points to ensure proper interaction for Task 3.4 (e.g., questionnaire distribution).	

Action ID	Action description	Alignment with EPOS Science Program 2024–2028
WP4	<p>A1. The SCC should support the implementation of the user engagement plan described in D4.1. To achieve this, the SCC should i. keep TCS actively engaged through regular communication using the contacts list; ii. encourage their involvement in the user strategy by promoting participation in training activities; iii. facilitate the inclusion of their representatives in programme committees for schools and events; vi. encourage and support early career researchers (ECR) to actively participate in EPOS activities.</p>	SO3
	<p>A2. The SCC should support the re-establishment of the User Feedback Group (UFG). To achieve this, the SCC should nominate candidates (expert researchers and ECRs) to ensure broad disciplinary coverage.</p>	
WP5	<p>A1. The SCC should coordinate with the WP5 coordination team to plan and participate in activities of mutual benefits with European and international partners. The implementation should be guided by the detailed roadmap for implementing international collaborations (D5.2)</p>	SO6
	<p>A2. The SCC should support the mapping of research organizations within EPOS RI participating in EOSC initiatives, clarifying their roles, responsibilities, and commitments in representing EPOS RI.</p>	
WP6	<p>A1. Building upon the insights and discussions from the EPOS Days 2025 session “EPOS in the national landscapes,” the SCC, should support the WP6 coordination team to establish a dedicated task force aimed at to facilitate communication between EPOS ERIC and the National nodes, sharing best practices and fostering mutual learning.</p>	Cross-cutting (Science Program & Sustainability Plan)
	<p>A2. The SCC should further support WP6 in engaging representatives from Ireland, Hungary, and the Czech Republic in the National Authorities Consultation Board (NACB).</p>	

Legend – EPOS Science Program 2024–2028 Strategic Objectives (SO):

SO1 Ensuring smooth and seamless access to solid Earth science data and services; **SO2** Enhancing and advancing services for solid Earth science; **SO3** Enlarging, widening and empowering the user community; **SO4** Implementing principles of Open Science and FAIR data management and contributing to e-science innovation; **SO5** Amplifying and spreading the societal value of EPOS; **SO6** Strengthening European and international cooperation and positioning of EPOS.

4. Conclusions and next steps

Deliverable D6.1 represents the first consolidated report on the optimization and evolution of EPOS RI produced within the EPOS ON project. It establishes a structured baseline of key results and recommendations derived from the first year of project implementation and from governance-level discussions within the Optimization and Evolution Board (OEB) and with the EPOS ERIC Service Coordination Committee (SCC).

The actions presented in this report support EPOS ERIC and its governance bodies in addressing key strategic dimensions of EPOS evolution, including service integration, societal relevance, user engagement, European and international collaboration, and sustainability. By linking each action to the EPOS Science Program 2024–2028 Strategic Objectives, the deliverable ensures transparency, traceability, and alignment with EPOS strategic priorities.

As next steps, WP6 will: (1) continue the six-monthly monitoring cycle through Internal Reports prepared by WP leaders, consolidated and discussed within the OEB, and shared with the SCC; and (2) strengthen SCC engagement by issuing a short periodic “WP highlights” update, based on WP leaders’ inputs, to flag key ongoing activities and clear requests requiring SCC involvement for the following period.

This iterative monitoring and interaction process will feed into Deliverable *D6.2 - Final Report on the Optimization and Evolution of EPOS RI (M34)*, which will consolidate the results and actions developed throughout the project and provide the final set of recommendations, discussed within the OEB and with the SCC, to support the long-term evolution and sustainability of EPOS RI.